

TECHNOLOGIES FOR MEASURING INTERNAL TEMPERATURES OF MODERN HEATING SYSTEMS IN HEAT SUPPLY

Abdullayev Shakhzod Khusniddin ugli

Uzbekistan GTL, Operator

abdullayevshakxzod@gmail.com

+998908691321 +998908989989

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8398587>

Abstract. This article is focused on small and medium capacity local heating boilers, together with excessive fuel consumption, lead to a significant non-ecological state of the environment. Therefore, the increase of large-scale thermal plants (IS) will lead to relief from additional fuel extraction. It is known that the main cost of the amount of heat used for utility, residential and public buildings (heating of buildings, ventilation, air condensation and hot water supply) is the cost of heating buildings.

Key words: temperature, heat flow, flux, ventilation, human heat, internal barriers, working zone, height limit, lanterns, slat, pipe, rip, infiltration

ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ИЗМЕРЕНИЯ ВНУТРЕННИХ ТЕМПЕРАТУР СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СИСТЕМ ОТОПЛЕНИЯ ПРИ ТЕПЛОСНАБЖЕНИИ

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена котлам местного отопления малой и средней мощности, которые в сочетании с чрезмерным потреблением топлива приводят к значительному неэкологическому состоянию окружающей среды. Таким образом, увеличение числа крупномасштабных тепловых электростанций (ИС) приведет к освобождению от дополнительной добычи топлива. Известно, что основной стоимостью количества тепла, используемого для коммунальных, жилых и общественных зданий (отопление зданий, вентиляция, конденсация воздуха и горячее водоснабжение), является стоимость отопления зданий.

Ключевые слова: температура, тепловой поток, флюкс, вентиляция, сердце человека, внутренние барьеры, рабочая зона, ограничение по высоте, фонари, планка, труба, разрыв, инфильтрация.

The useful heat output of any heating circuit consists of the sum of the heat flow transferred to the heat devices through the heat pipes and the heat lost during the movement in the distance between the pipes. Although the flow of heat consumed in the process of movement in the pipes is not very large, it still constitutes some part of the total useful heat flow. To calculate the useful heat flow, first of all, it is necessary to determine the heat flow from the external walls of the building to the outside air, which keeps the temperature in each room at a certain level. In short, it is necessary to fill the wasted heat flow with the heat supplied to the building with the help of heat devices.¹ In addition, the heat flow from the heating equipment is used for heating the air passing through the filtration process, equipment inside the building, etc.

It is known that in addition to heating devices, there are other sources of heating in the building. The main sources of heat in the building can be lighting equipment, technological equipment, additional heat emitted from people and the kitchen. Therefore, together with the determination of the absolute amount of heat supplied to each room from the heating devices, all the amounts of heat brought into the building from additional sources and consumed from external

¹ Anufriev L.N., Kozheynov I.A., Pozin G.M. Thermal engineering calculations of agricultural production buildings. M.: Stroizdat 1974-221

barriers should be taken into account in all periods of the year (summer, winter and changing periods)².

It is known that according to the law of conservation of energy, the flow of heat entering the building and the heat flowing out of the building should be equal to each other. In general, to calculate the heat balance of buildings, heat flows entering the building and spending through external barriers are determined. In order to determine the heat capacity of the heating system, the heat balance is determined using the following formula:

$$Q_i = \Delta Q = Q_{to's} + Q_{h.a} + Q_{t.i}$$

there: $Q_{to's}$ is the heat flux lost through external barriers;

$Q_{h.a}$ - heat used to heat the air entering the room;

$Q_{t.i}$ - heat flow released as a result of technological and household processes or consumed by the economy;

$Q_{h.a}$ is the missing part of the heat.

If, as a result of the heat balance calculation, there is a lack of heat, additional heat devices are installed in the building rooms, if there is excess heat, the amount of excess heat is absorbed by means of ventilation. Inside a number of buildings, most of the heat content is from human heat. In such a room (lecture room in higher educational institutions, cinema, theater, circus rooms, etc.), the temperature of the internal air is reduced. This reduced temperature is provided by heating devices, and the increase in air temperature and its return to normal is due to the heat released from the gathered people. Often, the calculated heat capacity of heating equipment in public buildings is equal to the amount of heat consumed. To determine the power of heating systems and to fully calculate all their equipment (the number of boilers and their heat-producing surface, heating equipment, calculated amounts of heat and their transfer to consumers; calculation of heat pipes), the external barrier of buildings The remaining heat flow should be determined based on the requirements of QMQ 2.04.05-97, QMQ 2.01.04-94 and QMQ 2.01.01-97.

As a result of thermal physical calculations of external barriers, efficient constructions for barriers are adopted for the volume-planning solution of buildings, according to the laws of thermal physics of construction. Therefore, efficient external barrier constructions, where the heat is physically selected with literacy, lead to saving the thermal power of heating systems. Part of the heat flow from the buildings depends on the influence of the wind, especially if the high-rise buildings are built bare in the direction of the wind, the heat consumption is significantly greater. On the contrary, heat consumption is lower in places protected from the wind direction and in buildings built inside the city. Therefore, in order to protect the buildings from the wind, special beams are installed that repel the wind force from the surface of the outer wall. The heat lost from the building under the influence of wind is called additional heat flow³.

So, the heat consumed in the building is of two types, the first one is the main one, and the second one is an additional heat flow.

The main heat loss from the building is from the following structures: floor surface, external wall surface, external window area, external door area and roof covering.

² Имомов Ш. Ж. “ Процесс теплопередачи при возвратнопоступательном движении фаз с пульсирующей загрузкой биомассы”//Гелиотехника, № 2, 2009с.65- 71.

³ Растимешин С. А. Обоснования параметров локальных электрообогревателей для молодняка сельскохозяйственных животных. Автореф. на сонск. д-ра техн. Наук.- М. 1996. 40с.

The following should be taken into account from the sources of additional heat flow⁴:

1. If the height of civil buildings exceeds 4 meters, 25 percent of the calculated basic and additional heat consumption, then 15 percent of additional heat should be taken for each meter of height. This additional heat consumption does not apply to production buildings and stairs.

2. If the wind speed is 5-10 m/s, 2 percent additional heat is obtained, if it has a speed of more than 10 m/s, 3 percent additional heat is obtained.

3. If the outer doors of large buildings are provided with a warm air curtain, the additional heat consumption given to the outer doors is taken into account.

4. In general, the amount of additional heat for typical buildings is 16 percent of the main heat.

In order to determine the heat flux lost from external barrier structures, the surface surfaces of each barrier should be determined separately based on a certain rule⁵.

We determine the surface area (F , m²) and the linear size of the barriers based on the following rules:

1. To determine the surface of windows, doors and lanterns (skylight), the smallest dimensions of their position are taken.

2. To determine the surface of the floor and ceiling, the measurement is taken from the middle of the thickness of the internal walls to the internal surface of the external walls.

3. External wall surfaces are determined in the following order:

A. The height of the wall of the first floor - if the floor is made of earth, it is taken from its surface to the surface of the floor of the second floor; if the floor is on a slat (wooden riser), the measurement is taken over the compacted ground, that is, from the base of the slat support to the floor level of the second floor, if there is an unheated basement, then the 1st floor the size from the bottom level of the cover to the level of the floor of the second floor is accepted.

B. For the height of the walls located between the floors, the distance above the floor of the floor to the floor of the floor above it is taken.

D. For the uppermost wall of a multi-story building, the distance from the surface of the floor of the upper floor to the top level of the attic covering structure is taken.

C. For upper floor wall height, the measurement is taken from the floor to the roof surface without the attic.

E. In the history of the building, the size of the external wall of a room that is not located in a corner is the distance between the axes passing between the internal barriers, the size of the external wall in a room located in a corner is the distance from the external surface of the external barrier to the axis of the internal barrier distance in is accepted.

G. For internal wall surfaces, the internal dimensions of the baffles are acceptable.

E. If the area of the floor surface is located in the corner, after dividing the length and width into zones every 2 meters, the pipe of the first zone is accepted twice as much. Rip - for an unheated floor (Fig. 1)

⁴ Avezov R.R., Orlov A.Yu. "Solar heating and hot water supply systems" Т.: "Fan". 1988- 282s

⁵ Растимешин С. А. Обоснования параметров локальных электрообогревателей для молодняка сельскохозяйственных животных. Автореф. на соиск. д-ра техн. Наук.- М. 1996. 40с.

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